

Predicted mean soil depth of water uptake differs among crop species but does not change with increased crop diversity

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Summary

Water is a limiting resource in crop production and with the prediction that drought events increase in frequency and severity, drought-resilient crop production is one major challenge to ensure food security. Intercropping of different crop species, which show differences in hydrological niches, is one solution to reduce competition for water. In this study, the soil depth of water uptake of different crop species was investigated and how these water uptake patterns change with increasing crop diversity. Stable isotope analyses of soil and plant water was used to predict mean soil depth of water uptake of the different crop species. Results show that soil depth of water uptake differs among crop species but is not changed by crop diversity. The choice of intercrops with distinguishable hydrological niches can be important in water-limited crop production.

Key words: Drought resilience, intercropping; mixed cropping; stable hydrogen isotopes; water use

Introduction

Water is, among other resources, a limiting factor of agricultural production (Sinclair, 1994). Additionally, it is predicted that drought events will become more frequent and more severe throughout Europe (Spinoni *et al.*, 2018). Water limitation in crop production can lead to reduced transpiration and photosynthesis rates and, thus, to lower yield (Lipiec *et al.*, 2013). Hence, drought-resilient crop production is a major challenge to ensure food security.

Intercropping (i.e. the cultivation of two or more crops in the same field) can be one solution to sustain productivity during such drought events. Intercropping, compared to sole cropping, can support water complementarity among neighbouring plants due to differences in hydrological niches of the different crop species (O’Keefe *et al.*, 2019). Hence, intercropping can lead to higher water-use efficiency and increased yield, compared to sole cropping (Morris & Garrity, 1993; Yin *et al.*, 2020). Differentiation of plant species into hydrological niches has already been shown in grasslands (O’Keefe *et al.*, 2019), natural systems (Silvertown *et al.*, 2015) and among tree species (Schwendenmann *et al.*, 2015).

So far, little is known if and how crop species differentiate into hydrological niches. One study showed that summer corn and cotton exhibit different water uptake patterns (Wang *et al.*, 2010). However, studies looking at other crop species are lacking and it is unknown how these water uptake patterns change with increasing crop diversity.

To close this gap, a field experiment was carried out with the aim (1) to study at which soil depth the different crop species are extracting water from and (2) to investigate if the soil depth of water uptake changes with increasing crop diversity. The following hypotheses were formulated: (1) the soil depth of water uptake differs among crop species and (2) increasing crop diversity leads to further differentiation in soil depth of the water uptake patterns of coexisting crop species.

To test these hypotheses, six different crop species were grown in monocultures, 2-species mixtures and 3-species mixtures in separate plots placed in the field. Soil and plant water were extracted and analysed for stable hydrogen isotopic composition. Mean soil depth of water uptake by crop species in the different treatments was predicted from stable hydrogen isotopic composition of soil samples taken at specific depths.

Materials and Methods

A field experiment was established near Zürich, Switzerland (longitude 8°29'58.6176" E, latitude 47°26'20.4612" N). Six crop species from three different functional groups were used, including the two cereal species spring barley (*Hordeum vulgare* var. Atrika) and spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum* var. Fiorina), the two legume species faba bean (*Vicia faba* var. Fanfare) and pea (*Pisum sativum* var. Astronaute) and the two oilseed herbs linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* var. Marquise) and rapeseed (*Brassica napus* subsp. *napus* var. Campino). These crop species were grown in monocultures, 2-species mixtures of all possible combinations and 3-species mixtures of all possible combinations among functional groups. The cultures were established in the field in plots measuring 0.5 m × 0.5 m, separated by a metal fence to a depth of 30 cm. The arrangement of the plots followed a randomised complete block design with three blocks (each replicate in one block) and each block containing 32 randomly arranged plots (29 plots occupied by plants and three plots without any plants (control plots)). The seeds were sown by hand on 6 of May 2019 with the recommended densities of the retailer (1.8 kg ac⁻¹ for barley, 2.1 kg m⁻¹ for wheat, 2.5 kg ac⁻¹ for bean, 2.75 kg ac⁻¹ for pea, 0.6 kg ac⁻¹ for linseed and 0.06 kg ac⁻¹ for rapeseed).

Soil and plant samples for δ²H analysis were collected on 25 of June 2019. For the soil samples, eight soil cores were sampled in the control plots at the following depths: 0 m (surface), 0.05 m, 0.1 m, 0.15 m, 0.2 m, 0.3 m, 0.5 m and 0.75 m. For the plant samples, the root crown of one or three (linseed, because of the small stature) individuals per treatment and species was collected. The root crown has already shown to be best for investigating source water of plants (Barnard *et al.*, 2006). Soil and plant samples were collected in 12 mL glass vials closed with a cap containing a chlorobutyl rubber septum (Exetainer[®], Labco Limited) and stored in the freezer at -20°C until further processing.

Water from soil and plant water was extracted with a Cryogenic vacuum method (Dalton, 1988). Subsequently, stable hydrogen isotopic composition of extracted soil and plant water was analysed with a TC/EA high-temperature conversion/elemental analyser coupled with a DeltaPlus XP mass spectrometer via a ConFlo III interface (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany). The ratio of stable hydrogen isotopic composition (²H/¹H) of the sample is expressed in the δ-notation (Eq. 1), adjusted relative to VSMOW-SLAP (Coplen, 1988).

$$\delta^{2H} = \left(\frac{\left(\frac{2H}{1H}\right)_{sample}}{\left(\frac{2H}{1H}\right)_{VSMOW}} - 1 \right) * 1000\text{‰} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

The statistical analysis was carried out in R version 4.0.2 (R Core Team, 2020). First, a linear mixed-effect model was used with the soil depth as response variable, soil δ²H as fixed effect and plots nested in blocks as a random term (packages “lme4” (Bates *et al.*, 2015)). Mean soil depth of water uptake of the plant δ²H was then predicted (predict.merMod from the lme4 package). Second,

Fig. 1. Predicted mean soil depth of water uptake (mean \pm standard error of the mean) of the six different crop species barley (a), bean (b), linseed (c), wheat (d), pea (e) and rapeseed (f) grown in monoculture (white bars), 2-species mixture (medium grey bars) and 3-species mixture (dark grey bars). The species mean is displayed with a dotted line. Replicate numbers are also indicated.

to explain the predicted mean soil depth through our experimental treatments, a linear mixed effects model and a type-I ANOVA with the Satterthwaite method was carried out (package “lmerTest” (Kuznetsova *et al.*, 2017)). The model included the fixed effects of species (barley, wheat, bean, pea, linseed or rapeseed), diversity (monoculture vs mixture) and mixture diversity (2-species mixture vs 3-species mixture) and the random effects of plots nested in blocks and species composition.

Results

The soil profile showed decreasing $\delta^2\text{H}$ with increasing soil depth ($P < 0.0001$). The $\delta^2\text{H}$ values of the soil depth can be distinguished up to 0.5 m (Table 1). With the soil depths and the corresponding calculated $\delta^2\text{H}$ value, mean soil depth of water uptake was predicted.

Table 1. The soil depth and the corresponding calculated $\delta^2\text{H}$. $\delta^2\text{H}$ was calculated with a linear mixed-effect model, with the soil depth as fixed effect and plots nested in blocks as random effects

Soil depth (m)	Calculated $\delta^2\text{H}$ (‰)	Groups
0	-30.68 ± 0.76	a
0.05	-39.00 ± 0.76	b
0.1	-44.15 ± 0.76	c
0.15	-51.02 ± 0.76	d
0.2	-56.79 ± 0.76	e
0.3	-63.46 ± 0.76	f
0.5	-71.23 ± 0.76	g
0.75	-70.79 ± 0.76	g

The predicted mean soil depth of water uptake differed among species (Table 2). Most of water was taken up at depths between 0.1 m and 0.2 m (Fig. 1). Rapeseed took up water at the greatest soil depth with a predicted mean soil depth of water uptake of 0.28 m. Pea, on the other hand, showed the shallowest predicted mean soil depth of water uptake with a species mean of 0.11 m. The other crop species showed very similar species means.

The increasing crop diversity had no effect on the predicted mean soil depth of water uptake (Table 2). However, as for barley, bean, linseed and pea, a shallower soil depth with increasing diversity was visible (Fig. 1). Rapeseed tended to take up water from deeper soil layers when grown in mixtures.

Table 2. Results of mixed effects type I ANOVA with the different treatments species (barley, wheat, bean, pea, linseed and rapeseed), diversity (monocultures vs mixtures), mixture diversity (2-species mixtures vs 3-species mixtures) and their interactions. SS: sum of squares, MS: mean of squares, numDF: degrees of freedom of term, denDF: degrees of freedom of error term, F-value: variance ratio, P-value: error probability. P-values in bold are significant with $\alpha=0.05$

	SS	MS	numDF	DenDF	F-value	P-value
species	4000	800	5	105.05	20.24	< 0.0001
diversity	19.8	19.79	1	29.59	0.50	0.48
mixture diversity	36.6	36.64	1	11.465	0.93	0.36
species \times diversity	186.5	37.29	5	40.34	0.94	0.46
species \times mixture diversity	58.2	11.63	5	109.78	0.29	0.92

Discussion

The predicted mean soil depth of water uptake differed between crop species, supporting the first hypothesis. This was expected, because crop species show different root distributions (Fan *et al.*,

2016). The predicted mean soil depth of water uptake for pea was also expected. Pea has already been shown to have rather shallow roots compared to other crop species (Hamblin & Hamblin, 1985). Rapeseed, on the other hand, surprisingly took up most of the water in deeper soil. Indeed, rooting depth of rapeseed has never been shown to be exceptionally deep (Fan *et al.*, 2016). However, rooting depth and root distribution are not the only factors influencing water uptake (Molz, 1971). Environmental factors such as soil water content and precipitation history, but also physiological factors such as intrinsic water use efficiency can influence water uptake of the plants (Liu *et al.*, 2011; Nippert & Knapp, 2007; Ding *et al.* 2020).

Diversity played a minor role in explaining the differences in water uptake patterns among crop species. Thus, the second hypothesis has to be rejected. However, a consistent pattern that higher crop diversity led to increased predicted mean soil depth of water uptake cannot be ignored, even though this effect could not be validated statistically. Nevertheless, the fact that different crop species take up water at different soil depths is of great value for crop production. Crop species grown together with distinguishable hydrological niches can reduce belowground competition for water.

Anyhow, one has to consider that the predicted mean soil depth of water uptake is an integration of all the water sources in all the soil depth from where the crops are taking their water. Thus, an approach that allows precise partitioning of water from different sources might be more appropriate, especially when looking at the diversity effect.

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